

Detection of GAN Generated Images Related Poisoning Attacks in Federated Learning Systems

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Abstract—The rise of Generative Adversarial Networks has raised significant concerns about poisoning attacks in Federated Learning systems. Attackers often inject synthetic images created by these networks to harm model performance and compromise user privacy. While many existing solutions focus on specific threats, our study introduces a new machine-learning algorithm that effectively detects models using synthetic data and defends against label-flipping attacks. This dual detection method not only enhances the reliability of the system but also ensures that it can accurately tell apart real models and synthetic models. By addressing these critical challenges, we aim to improve the overall resilience of Federated Learning systems against emerging threats. To validate our method, we will conduct thorough tests across various attack scenarios, evaluating its performance in different settings. Our goal is to strengthen the security of the system and promote its wider use in a variety of applications, ultimately fostering greater trust in these advanced technologies.

Index Terms—Generative Adversarial Nets, Federated Learning, Label Flipping, Poisoning Attacks

I. INTRODUCTION

Federated Learning (FL) is a decentralized learning paradigm that enables multiple participants to collaboratively train a global model without directly sharing their local data [6]. In FL, clients train models on their private datasets, and a central server aggregates the model parameters (weights) from a randomly selected subset of clients. This iterative process continues until the global model converges. One widely adopted algorithm in this setting is Federated Averaging (FedAvg) [12], which effectively addresses challenges associated with non-independent and identically distributed (non-IID) and unbalanced data across clients. To ensure privacy, the server does not access client data or monitor their training processes.

Therefore FL is vulnerable to poisoning attacks, where adversaries manipulate local models to inject poisoned updates into the global model[1]. Attackers create poisoned updates to influence global parameters, causing the model to learn harmful patterns[13]. Key factors contributing to this vulnerability include the large number of participants, the server’s inability to verify local updates, and secure aggregation protocols that prevent auditing. While defenses exist, they often fail against advanced adversaries, particularly those using Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs) to develop synthetic data. GANs

Fig. 1: FL system with malicious client

produce realistic poisoned data that evade traditional detection methods, which assume predictable attack patterns.

This paper highlights the limitations of current defenses against GAN-based poisoning attacks, especially with image data. Traditional label-flipping attacks are constrained by the availability of real data, limiting their impact. However, by leveraging GANs, adversaries can generate an unlimited amount of synthetic data with flipped labels, significantly amplifying the attack’s effectiveness. We propose a novel detection mechanism to identify malicious clients using GAN-generated data. Our empirical evaluation demonstrates that this method effectively distinguishes benign from adversarial updates, strengthening the privacy and robustness of FL systems. Our work underscores the need for advanced defenses to counter evolving adversarial threats, particularly GAN-based attacks.

A. Our Contributions

We highlight our key contributions as follows:

- We identify models trained on real data versus those trained on real data with label-flipped samples and those poisoned with GAN-generated label-flipped data, providing an effective defense against such attacks.

- We extend our mechanism to also distinguish between models trained on real data and those trained on GAN-generated datasets.

Our detection system offers state-of-the-art security for FL by targeting multiple data poisoning attacks. We also used Grad-CAM heatmap analysis to visually inspect and confirm models trained on GAN-generated data, enhancing transparency and interpretability in detecting malicious behavior.

The structure of the paper is as follows: In Section II, we review related work and offer a comprehensive comparison between our method and previous approaches. Section III covers the preliminaries necessary for understanding the context and background of our research. Section IV introduces the attack models used in our study. Section V explains both the existing detection mechanisms and our novel detection mechanism. Section VI validates the novelty of our approach, demonstrating its effectiveness in real-world scenarios. Finally, Section VII concludes the paper and highlights prospective paths for further research.

II. RELATED WORK

A. Poisoning Attacks Against Machine Learning

Poisoning attacks threaten machine learning by injecting malicious data to degrade performance. While well-studied in simpler models like SVMs, deep neural networks remain vulnerable [9]. Generative Poisoning Attacks using autoencoders [11] demonstrate how easily DNNs can be compromised, highlighting the need for mitigation. Defenses like adversarial training, data sanitization [10], and anomaly detection exist, but challenges persist against advanced poisoning strategies.

B. Poisoning Attacks in FL

FL poisoning attacks can compromise data integrity or manipulate model updates to affect the integrity of the global model. Data poisoning and model poisoning are the two main categories of malicious attacks. Adversaries alter the training data to deceive the model through data poisoning. The attack can either be clean-label, where the data is subtly modified but the labels are preserved, or dirty-label [5]. An attacker would alter the local model updates in the model poisoning attack before forwarding them to the central server. In doing this, the attackers want to result in modifying the global model at the time of aggregation and cause targeted misclassifications. Recent works, like PoisonGAN [13], employ GANs to automatically generate poisoned data. This is enabled by the presence of GANs, which in turn makes it easier for adversaries to construct stealthy yet effective adversarial samples and thus makes the detection even harder. These sophisticated poisoning attacks will motivate the need for robust detection mechanisms, while the appearance of GAN-based methods is becoming increasingly common in FL systems.

C. Defense Mechanism in FL

Solutions like Foolsgold [3] and Krum [7] have significant limitations when it comes to defending against poisoning attacks in FL. Importantly, no existing defense mechanisms have been developed to specifically detect models trained on GAN-generated images, leaving a critical gap in current approaches. This creates an urgent need for more robust and adaptive mechanisms capable of ensuring model integrity. Table I compares various methods used for detecting poisoning attacks in FL, including the robustness of each method to real and GAN-based attacks.

TABLE I: Comparison of Methods for State-of-the-Art Poisoning Attack Detection

Criteria	Krum [7]	Multi-Krum [7]	Foolsgold [3]	Median [2]	Our Work
Robust to Sybil Attacks	Partial	Partial	✓	✗	✓
Detection of Real Data Poisoning	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Detection of GAN Data Poisoning	✗	✗	✗	✗	✓
Detection of GAN Clients	✗	✗	✗	✗	✓
XAI for GAN detection	✗	✗	✗	✗	✓

III. PRELIMINARIES

In this section, we provide a brief overview of the fundamental concepts of FL and introduce GANs to enhance the understanding of our proposed defense mechanism.

A. FL System

In traditional centralized training, users upload their data to a server, raising privacy concerns. FL improves privacy by having users send only local model updates rather than raw data. Each of the n users trains a local model and uploads gradients g_i^k , which are averaged to update the global model as follows:

$$m_{i+1} = m_i + \frac{1}{n} \sum_{k=1}^n g_i^k \quad (1)$$

In this equation, m_i is the current global model, g_i^k represents the gradients from the user k , and m_{i+1} is the updated global model. By averaging the weights of all users [8], the system updates the global model while preserving the privacy of individual datasets.

B. Generative Adversarial Nets

GANs have become an inevitable aspect of generating synthetic data. Ian Goodfellow et al. introduced the concept of GAN in 2014 [4]. GANs include two neural networks

known as Generator G and Discriminator D . They work on the principle of adversarial training. The G learns to generate highly realistic samples, while the D learns to distinguish fake and real data, as in Fig. 2. Adversarial training is a min-max game, where both networks are learning iteratively to improve their performance. The learning process can be represented as in Equation 2 [4].

The G takes random noise z as input and produces synthetic data samples x_{gen} . During the training process, from backpropagation, G will learn the probability of target features and update its neural network parameters. D is a classifier that differentiates between the real data set $\mathcal{D}_{\text{train}}$ and the synthetic samples x_{gen} and learns the probability of the target class with given features during back-propagation.

$$\min_G \max_D V(D, G) = \mathbb{E}_{x \sim p_{\text{data}}(x)} [\log D(x)] + \mathbb{E}_{z \sim p_z(z)} [\log(1 - D(G(z)))] \quad (2)$$

In this equation $p_{\text{data}}(x)$ represents the real data distribution and $p_z(z)$ denotes the random noise vector. The discriminator $D(x)$ will give the probability that the input x is a real sample.

Fig. 2: GAN based data generation

IV. ATTACK MODELS

In this section, we begin by outlining the threat model, detailing the learning scenario, the attacker’s objectives, and their capabilities. Following that, we discuss the poisoning attacks on the FL system and demonstrate the effectiveness of our detection algorithm through experimental evaluations.

A. Threat Model

1) *Learning Scenario*: In our threat model (the global model, in this case, is an image classifier), multiple participants ($N \geq 2$) collaborate to train a global model using their available local datasets. Some participants may be the attackers who aim to poison the global model by mimicking benign participants. Malicious clients can only access the global model via the FL process, without control over the server’s aggregation algorithm or the learning process of other participants. They follow the FL protocol, but update their local models with poisoned data.

2) *Attacker’s Capabilities*: Attackers act as honest participants, but use GANs to generate poisoned data resembling training sets of others. They actively manipulate training inputs and updates, fully understanding the agreed-upon model structure.

3) *Attacker’s Goals*: The attackers aim to corrupt the global model by introducing poisoned GAN-generated samples into their local datasets. These samples resemble benign data but are label-flipped to degrade model accuracy. The intent is to modify what the model predicts for benign inputs after the server accumulates the local updates.

B. Attack Construction

1) *Attack Overview*: The poisoning attack in FL involves three steps: first, the attacker generates poisoned samples using a GAN and incorporates them into the local dataset. These samples are mislabeled and used to calculate poisoned local parameters. The attacker then uploads these altered parameters to the global server, intending to bias the global model to misclassify inputs during inference.

2) *GAN Data Generation*: The malicious clients use a GAN to generate x_{gen} that mimics the real participant data. By acting as a benign participant, the attacker replicates the global model as the D in their GAN architecture. Throughout the FL rounds, D stays in sync with global model updates, guiding the G to create realistic synthetic datasets. These generated samples are assigned to labels from the label space Y and form the poisoned dataset $\mathcal{D}_{\text{poison}}$, which the attacker submits to poison the global model. The attacker will use this $\mathcal{D}_{\text{poison}}$ during the FL training process to degrade the accuracy of the global model.

3) *GAN-based Poisoning Attack*: The poisoning attack strategy allows an attacker to inject synthetic, mislabeled data into their training set and upload corrupted model updates to the central server:

- 1) In an FL system, there are benign participants with real data and attackers with malicious intent. Each participant updates the global model iteratively.
- 2) Benign participants download the global model, update it using their private dataset, and upload improved versions to the server.
- 3) Attackers, however, download the global model, generate synthetic data using a GAN, and assign incorrect labels to this data, creating a poisoned dataset. They then train their local model on this dataset and submit corrupted updates to the server.
- 4) This process repeats until the global model converges.

The attack relies on the effectiveness of the discriminator to generate synthetic data and degrade model performance through label-flipping. Algorithm 1 describes a generalized version of this attack with multiple attackers.

V. DETECTION MODEL

Detecting clients trained in GAN-generated data and identifying GAN-based poisoning in FL is crucial. Existing defenses

Algorithm 1 PoisonGen

Require: Training dataset D_{trainset} ; Global model G_t ; Noise data $Z_{\text{noisedata}}$; Label set Y .
Ensure: Generated poisoned dataset D_{poison} .
Initializing generator network G and discriminator network D .
for each global iteration $t = 1$ to T **do**
 Update D using the global model G_t .
 for each local epoch $e_k = 1$ to E **do**
 for each noise batch b from Z_{noise} **do**
 Use G to generate a fake sample x_{fake} .
 Forward x_{fake} to the discriminator D .
 if x_{fake} is classified as target class y_k **then**
 Store generated sample $x_k \leftarrow x_{\text{fake}}$.
 return x_k .
 else
 Optimize G according to the loss function (Eq. 1).
 end if
 end for
 if label of x_k matches the target $y_k \in Y$ **then**
 Reassign label y_n to x_k as chosen by the attacker.
 Append (x_k, y_n) to D_{poison} .
 end if
 end for
end for
return D_{poison} .

like Foolsgold and Krum are ineffective against such attacks. We propose GAN_Det, a novel detection mechanism that accurately identifies poisoning clients and models using GAN data, strengthening FL against advanced threats.

A. Vulnerability of Existing Defense Mechanisms

Foolsgold counters Sybil attacks by limiting similar updates, but fails with GAN-based data, which mimics real data and reduces weight diversity. This undermines cosine similarity, allowing attacks to compromise the global model.

B. Development of Detection Mechanism

Our novel detection mechanism approach uses statistical checks to detect anomalies by analyzing the variability of extracted features, preventing poisoned models from being integrated into the global model.

Algorithm 2 GAN_Det

Require: Client updates u_1, u_2, \dots, u_n , Dedicated test dataset D
Initialize weight vector $wv \leftarrow \mathbf{1}$
for each client i **do**
 Use client update u_i to test on D and extract features f_i from the last layer of CNN
 Flatten f_i and compute $\sigma(f_i)$
 if $\sigma(f_i) < \tau$ **then**
 $wv[i] \leftarrow 0$ // Mark as malicious
 end if
end for
for each client i with $wv[i] \neq 0$ **do**
 for each parameter k in f_i **do**
 $w_{\text{acc}}[k] \leftarrow w_{\text{acc}}[k] + wv[i] \cdot u_i[k]$
 end for
end for

Each client model update is validated on a trusted data set on the server; features are extracted from the last CNN layer and flattened for analysis. The standard deviation of the flattened features is used as a detection measure. To set the threshold value, we use data sets with various ratios of real and GAN-poisoned data. This allows us to extract known benign and malicious features for testing. Feature-based detection is preferable to looking at weights directly, since features are better reflections of the model’s internal representations and are more sensitive to the small imperfections introduced by synthetic input.

The validation-based grid search is then performed by trying an array of candidate values. For each value, the classification performance is quantified with respect to known labels. The optimal threshold is computed from the value that provides the best trade-off between true and false positive rates. Algorithm 2 outlines our aggregation strategy, which filters out clients with a lower standard deviation than the threshold, flagging them as malicious.

C. XAI detection model

In our proposed detection mechanism, we leveraged Explainable AI techniques to identify malicious clients in a FL system. After training the global model, the individual client models’ weights were saved. A test image from the training dataset was then used to generate Grad-CAM heatmaps for each client model. These heatmaps visually represented the decision-making process of each model, allowing us to interpret how each client model processed the same image.

VI. EXPERIMENTAL EVALUATION

A. Datasets and Model Setup

To evaluate the proposed algorithm, we engaged with gray-scale and color images. So, we conduct different dataset generation processes with two typical datasets, which are MNIST and CIFAR-10.

For MNIST, a custom CNN model is employed for image classification as a classifier. For CIFAR-10, the widely used ResNet-50 is utilized as a classifier. The summary of these classifier models is illustrated in Table II.

TABLE II: Global Model Architectures for both Data Sets

Classifier	MNIST	CIFAR-10
Structure	Conv(1,32,3,1)+ReLU Conv(32,64,3,1)+ReLU MaxPool2D(2,2) Dropout(0.25) FC(9216,128)+ReLU Dropout(0.5) FC(128,10) LogSoftmax(dim=1)	ResNet-50

B. Detection mechanism

In our study, we applied Fool’s Gold, Krum and GAN_Det to evaluate the effectiveness defense mechanisms against Un-target label-flipping attacks in FL. Specifically, we tested the defense mechanism against two types of attacks:

- Label Flipping Attacks on Real MNIST Images
- Label Flipping Attacks on GAN-generated MNIST Images

In addition to detecting label-flipping attacks, we also distinguished between models trained on real MNIST images and those trained on GAN-generated images

In this study, we evaluated the impact of label-flipping attacks on model accuracy using real and GAN-generated MNIST images. Each benign client received 4,000 correctly labeled images, while each malicious client had 4,000 label-flipped images. Using a 10-client FL setup, we varied the number of malicious clients to observe accuracy changes when they outnumbered or were outnumbered by benign clients.

Fig. 3: Accuracy change due to Poisoning Attack using Real and GAN Data

Fig 3 shows the effectiveness of synthetic data generated by GAN in FL. It showcases that using GAN data for training results in lower global model accuracy in both cases: scenarios with 3 out of 10 clients and 6 out of 10 clients are GAN users.

The results, depicted in Fig 4, exhibit the accuracy of the model over training rounds when subjected to label flipping attacks. The performance of the Foolsgold and Krum algorithms was notably effective in mitigating the impact of these attacks, as evidenced by their accuracy in comparison to the FedAvg algorithm. But our proposed Gan_Det method outperforms all three algorithms, demonstrating significantly better resilience against these attacks. Label-flipping attacks generally reduce model updates' variability; hence Gan_Det was excellent in flagging and excluding such clients. On the other hand, Foolsgold and Krum use geometric-based methods to catch malicious behavior, which may not work as well for some subtle malicious behavior.

Fig. 4: Detection of Label Flipping Attack using Real MNIST Images

(a) 30% malicious clients (b) 60% malicious clients

Fig. 5: Detection of Label Flipping Attack using GAN-generated MNIST Images

Fig 5 illustrates the effect of label-flipping attacks on model accuracy in an FL setting. The results show that with 30% and 60% malicious clients, the Foolsgold and Krum algorithms struggled to defend against these attacks, resulting in a notable decline in model accuracy. Gan_Det consistently maintained higher accuracy, because it deals with a more nuanced feature-based analysis that focuses on the distribution of updates rather than just comparing similarities.

Fig. 6: Accuracy Variation in Detection of Label Flipping Attacks with Evolving Malicious Clients

Fig. 6 presents the accuracy of the global model in a FL system when the malicious client count increases. Key observations reveal that the global model accuracy declines in both scenarios as the number of malicious clients rises. In particular, the accuracy remains higher for real MNIST label-flipped clients compared to GAN MNIST label-flipped clients. But, Gan_Det consistently achieved better accuracy across all scenarios, as it uses a feature-driven approach to identify inconsistent patterns in the weight updates that are indicative of poisoning.

Fig. 7: Comparison of Detection Performance: Original vs. GAN and Original vs. Poisoned GAN

While previous works focused on the development of mechanisms for detection to counter GAN-based poisoning attacks,

this paper will demonstrate that these same GAN-generated images being utilized in the training process can also be detected as part of a wider malicious scenario. Detection of these synthetic images is important because they can subtly manipulate model performance and further underline the importance of safeguarding FL models against various attack vectors. Fig 7 presents the performance of our algorithm in detecting GAN images and poisoned GAN images in federated learning systems.

Although synthetic data can serve valid purposes, such as data augmentation, privacy protection, and bias correction, it still affects the reliability of the FL system. Even without malicious intent, its presence can introduce unintended effects that compromise the integrity of the model. This highlights the need for effective detection mechanisms to ensure that the global model remains trustworthy and robust.

Fig. 8: Grad-CAM heatmap for real and GAN used models

Apart from the detection mechanism, Explainable AI (XAI) plays a crucial role in interpreting and understanding model decisions, making complex deep learning models more transparent. One such XAI technique is Grad-CAM, which provides visual explanations by highlighting important regions in an image that influence a model’s decision. The above Fig8 illustrates the Grad-CAM heatmaps generated for models trained on real data and GAN-generated data. It is visually apparent that models using GAN-generated data exhibit distinct heatmap patterns compared to those trained on real data. This clear visual differentiation highlights the effectiveness of the Grad-CAM method in identifying models that have used GAN-generated data.

VII. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORKS

This paper addresses the challenge of detecting clients utilizing GAN-generated images in federated learning, highlighting the limitations of existing defense mechanisms, such as Foolsgold and Krum, against sophisticated poisoning attacks. We developed a novel detection mechanism that effectively identifies both GAN-based poisoning attackers and models trained on GAN-generated images by analyzing model updates and applying statistical checks. In addition, we integrate Grad-CAM, a technique for visualizing model decisions, to further enhance the detection of malicious clients. Experiments with MNIST and CIFAR-10 datasets demonstrate that our detection mechanism outperforms existing defenses in scenarios involving label-flipping attacks on both real and GAN-generated data.

Future work will explore the application of the proposed detection mechanism to more complex and diverse datasets

to ensure scalability and effectiveness across a wide range of FL scenarios. Additionally, enhancements will be made to fine-tune the statistical methods used to differentiate benign from malicious clients, particularly as attackers develop more advanced GAN-generated data.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This work is partly supported by the European Union under the ENSURE-6G project (Grant Agreement No. 101182933) and the CONNECT phase 2 project by Research Ireland (Grant No. 13/RC/2077_P2).

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